

IMPROVEMENT OF THE CFRP COMPOSITE MIRROR SURFACE USING A REPLICA METHOD

T. Kamiya^{1*}, S. Utsunomiya¹, K. Komatsu¹, R. Shimizu¹

¹ Aerospace Research and Development Directorate, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, 2-1-1 Sengen, Tsukuba City, Ibaraki 305-5805, Japan

* Corresponding author (kamiya.tomohiro@jaxa.jp)

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1 Introduction

Recently, the observation performance required for satellite telescopes has been increasing ever-further due to the growing needs for earth observation to understand the mechanisms that cause abnormal weather phenomena, global warming or global climate change and astronomical observation for research into the Earth's origin or mechanisms of the universe. Accordingly, a range of measures to improve observation performance have been implemented, of which the most appropriate method is to enlarge the aperture diameter of the main mirror of telescopes. However, the maximum weight of the satellite is limited by the launch capacity of the rocket, meaning the main mirror and satellite structures must be lightweight and highly rigid.

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are ultra-lightweight, with a high elastic modulus, and their CTE can be tailored to low or zero over a wide temperature range, as shown in Fig. 1, making them widely applicable for satellite structures and mission sensor structures. Their dimensional stability is suitable for components requiring high accuracy such as radio reflectors and telescope structures. However, optical telescope mirrors, which require a nanometer standard surface roughness, are still commonly made of metal or glass, e.g. Be, ULE, Zerodur and SiC, and CFRP are not applied. CFRP surfaces have micro asperities (fiber print-through) caused by chemical and thermal shrinkage during curing as shown in Fig. 2. The surface roughness is a few hundred nm RMS when fabricated and too rough for optical telescope mirrors. Mirrors made of ULE or SiC can easily attain nanometer level standards for surface roughness by optical polishing, but it is difficult to reduce the weight due to the material properties and fabrication process. To ensure a good balance between rigidity and weight,

the rear side of mirrors made of ULE or SiC is commonly hollowed out from bulk material with a milling machine and with a rib structures constructed as shown in Fig. 3. Although this was successful in reducing the weight by more than 90% relative to the bulk material, this percentage remains limited due to the processable thickness of the rib wall and it cannot be made any lighter. Conversely, CFRP are superior in terms of the fabrication of thin wall structures by stacking thin prepreg layers and using honeycomb core sandwich structures, and have successfully reduced weight by more than 95%.

Fig. 1 CTE of typical materials used for space telescope mirrors [1]

Fig. 2 Fiber print-through on the CFRP surface [2]

Fig. 3 Rear structure of the ASTRO-F main mirror [3]

Fig. 4 Main mirror of the Hubble Space Telescope

Fig. 5 Mirror of the FRP skin/CFRP Flex Core

For example, the areal density of the main mirror of the Hubble Space Telescope made of ULE (Fig. 4) is 180 kg/m^2 and that of the infrared astronomical satellite named ASTRO-F made of SiC (Fig. 3) is 28 kg/m^2 [3]. Conversely, we fabricated the CFRP skin/CFRP honeycomb core sandwich mirror (Fig. 5) and achieved an areal density of under 10 kg/m^2 in a previous study [4]. Since the CFRP density is lower than that of other typical materials used for space telescope mirrors, CFRP/CFRP sandwich structures have a great advantage in terms of weight saving. If we can overcome the surface roughness problem caused by print-through, CFRP should

become the material of choice for large scale telescopes.

The fiber print-through observed on the CFRP surface after fabrication can be covered and removed by applying a replica technique, while the surface roughness can also be limited to within several tens of nm RMS [2]. The roughness of the coated surface can also be improved by polishing or resin coating conditions [5]. By optical-polishing or diamond turning, surface roughness to within 1~2 nm RMS was achieved [6].

In this paper, we report on progress in the improvement of the CFRP mirror surface roughness using only a replica method.

2 Specimen and test procedure

2.1 Specimen

To demonstrate the validity of the CFRP mirrors in terms of surface roughness at a nanometer level, we fabricated a concave mirror consisting of a CFRP/CFRP sandwich panel as shown in Fig. 6. The diameter was 150 mm, the thickness was 14 mm (both front and rear skins were 2 mm thick and the honeycomb core was 10 mm thick) and the radial curvature was 454 mm. The face skins were made of high elastic pitch graphite fibers (K1352U, Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc.) and a cyanate ester matrix resin (EX1515, TenCate). The reason why we selected cyanate ester resin as a matrix was because it has lower moisture absorption characteristics and should be less susceptible to atmospheric moisture than epoxy resin, which is commonly used as a matrix of CFRP [4]. The core was constructed from thin plain woven CFRP prepregs made of high elastic pitch graphite fibers (YSH-50A, Nippon Graphite Fiber Corp.) and a cyanate ester matrix resin (RS-3, TenCate) to flexible honeycomb core structures (UltraFlex®, Ultracor Inc.). During the fabrication of face skins, thin compliant prepreg layers were arranged in a quasi-isotropic configuration ($[0/45/-45/90]_{4s}$) onto a layup tool made of low expansion glass, which was optically polished to a surface roughness of $\lambda/20$ (equal to about 30 nm PV). The tool was selected to reduce the surface roughness of the skin by replicating the smoothness of the tool and the thermal strain caused by the difference in CTE between the skins and tool during curing. The stacked laminates were cured at

175°C for 2hr in an autoclave. The cured face skins and honeycomb core were then bonded using cyanate ester resin film adhesive (EX1516, TenCate) on the same glass tool. After sandwich adhesive bonding, the surface of the front face skin of the sandwich panels was coated by epoxy resin using the same glass tool as in the replica method. The steps of the replication process are sketched in Fig. 7: First, the surface of the layup tool was polished to the desired smoothness and mold release was spread on the tool, whereupon the epoxy resin for the replica coat, which was degassed in a vacuum, was spread thinly over the mold release. A honeycomb sandwich mirror was carefully adhered to the epoxy resin to avoid any air or dust particles infiltrating into the boundary face, and the resin was cured at room temperature. After bonding cure, the coated mirror was demolded and an aluminum evaporation coating was finally applied.

Fig. 7 Schematics of the replication process

(a) Before sandwich adhesive bonding

(b) After sandwich adhesive bonding and replica coating

Fig. 6 Specimen and measurement device

2.2 Test procedure

The surface roughness was measured before sandwich adhesive bonding and after replica coating using a Zygo NewView 7300, which is a 3D optical surface profiler as shown in Fig. 6. The basic measurement area selected was 0.4×0.4 mm in order to evaluate the micro roughness, while wider areas were also measured to examine the patterned indented surface or midfrequency ripples. The lateral and vertical resolutions of the measurements were $1 \mu\text{m}$ and 0.1 nm respectively and sufficiently precise

to observe the fiber print-through. Measurement positions were chosen at the center and 4 points around the mirrors, and the average and dispersion of these data were evaluated. Surface roughness was calculated against the best-fit spherical figure.

3 Test results

Figure 8 shows a surface map of the face skin, which was measured over an area of 12.5×12.5 mm before sandwich adhesive bonding. In Fig. 8 (a), there are two remarks. The first is that the orientation and magnitude of fiber print-through can be seen, with the green arrowed lines in this figure indicating the relatively-large print-through. The widths of these midfrequency ripples are about $1 \sim 2$ mm. Conversely, the fiber diameter for the CFRP skins was about $7 \mu\text{m}$, showing a significant difference in size between these ripples and the fiber diameter. Meanwhile, the second shows the orientations of these ripples mainly in 45° and -45° directions. However, the orientation of the outermost layer was horizontal in this figure, while those of the ripples coincide with the orientation of the second and third layers (45° and -45° respectively). These remarks mean that the resulting fiber print-through as shown in Fig. 8 (a) does not correspond to the geometry of single fibers in the outermost layer. Also, this implies that the relatively-large fiber print-through is the result of the underlying fiber tows transposing their geometry onto the surface during curing. Fig. 8 (b) shows a cross-sectional profile along the perpendicular line drawing in Fig. 8 (a). In this profile, micro asperities with short wavelength can be seen on the midfrequency ripples. It would appear that these micro asperities correspond to the microscopic linear pattern resembling a hair seam in Fig. 8 (a), which is likely to be attributable to the geometry of the single fibers of the outermost layer appearing onto the surface. This has been supported by detailed observation. Figure 9 (a) shows the micro roughness measured within the area 0.4×0.4 mm and this is a close up view of the center of Fig. 8 (a). In this figure, the orientation and magnitude of the micro asperities, as indicated by red arrowed lines, can be seen. The directions of almost all the micro asperities are horizontal and coincide with the orientation of the outermost layer. The widths of these micro asperities are about $10 \mu\text{m}$ and correlate closely to the fiber diameter. Figure 9 (b) shows the

cross-sectional profile, and the heights of the micro asperities can be seen as about $100 \sim 300$ nm. The deep valleys of the profile are likely to correspond to the spotty dent areas as shown in Fig. 9 (a). These dents are likely due to air or dust particles being mixed between the outermost prepreg layer and the layup tool during the fabrication process of the face skin. The average micro roughness evaluated within the 0.4×0.4 mm area is $21.41 \mu\text{m}$ PV and $0.51 \mu\text{m}$ RMS. The standard deviations of the roughness data from multiple locations are $3.99 \mu\text{m}$ (PV) and $0.33 \mu\text{m}$ (RMS), and there is significant variation among the data. It seems that the PV value of the average micro roughness is slightly high due to the depth of spotty dent areas. Figure 9 (c) shows the bearing ratio plot, otherwise known as 'Abbott-Firestone curve', which describes the surface texture of an object. Mathematically it is the cumulative probability density function of the surface profile's height. The x-axis is the bearing ratio and the y-axis is the depth from the highest peak.

Fig. 8 Midfrequency ripples of the mirror skin before sandwich adhesive bonding

Fig. 9 Micro roughness of the mirror skin before sandwich adhesive bonding

Fig. 11 Micro roughness of the mirror skin after replica coating

Fig. 10 Cross-sectional image of the face skin before sandwich adhesive bonding

Table 1 Micro roughness of the CFRP mirror surface measured within the area 0.4×0.4 mm

Micro roughness	before sandwich adhesive bonding	after replica coating
Average	21.41 μm PV 0.51 μm RMS 0.19 μm R_k	240.4 nm PV 5.1 nm RMS 9.38 nm R_k
Standard deviation	3.99 μm (PV) 0.33 μm (RMS) 0.14 μm (R_k)	98.8 nm (PV) 0.8 nm (RMS) 0.72 nm (R_k)

The R_k parameters (R_{pk} , R_k and R_{vk}) give a numerical summary of information contained in the bearing ratio curve, based on a division of the depth scale into three regions (peak region; middle, or core region; valley region) as shown in Figs. 9 (c) and 11 (c). The R_k value, which can evaluate the surface roughness without the height of spike shapes and the depth of spotty dent areas, is $0.19 \mu\text{m}$ on an average and the standard deviation is $0.14 \mu\text{m}$. Figure 10 shows a cross-sectional image of the face skin, which is found to match cross-sectional profile in Fig. 9 (b).

Figure 11 shows the micro roughness measured at about the same position and condition as Fig. 9 after replica coating. Note that the scale of height axis differs from Figs. 8 and 9. As compared with Fig. 9, it seems that the orientation and the magnitude of the micro asperities can be covered and removed from the surface by replica coating. Also, a relatively-large fiber print-through can be covered and removed. The micro roughness after the replica coating is 240.4 nm PV and 5.1 nm RMS on an average and the standard deviations are 98.8 nm (PV) and 0.8 nm (RMS) . As compared with the roughness of the layup tool, which is about 30 nm PV , the replicated surface is slightly rougher. The linear pattern appears scrubbed and spotty dent areas are apparent on the replicated surface, the asperities of which are thought to cause the slightly rougher quality. The orientation of the linear pattern is non-uniform and multi-directional. It would appear that the pattern is made while spreading the mold release agent or epoxy resin because these are liquid and spread by brush coating. Overpainting gradually is likely to leave brush traces on the surface in various directions. We consider this issue to be solvable by spreading it more carefully or using a gasiform mold release agent. Also, air or dust particles, which are mixed between the outermost prepreg layer and the layup tool during the fabrication process, are considered possibly responsible for the spotty dent areas.

Table 1 shows a comparison of the micro roughness before and after the replica coating. It is determined that the micro roughness of the face skin can be improved from $0.51 \mu\text{m RMS}$ to 5.1 nm RMS by replica coating.

4 Conclusions

We fabricated a CFRP skin/CFRP honeycomb core sandwich mirror to demonstrate the validity of the CFRP mirrors. The fiber print-through was grouped into 2 classes according to the wavelength: one being a relatively-large fiber print-through, which is the result of the underlying fiber tows transposing their geometry onto the surface during curing and the other is micro asperities, which is the geometry of the single fibers of the outermost layer appearing onto the surface. By applying a replica technique, the fiber print-through can be overcome and the surface roughness of the CFRP mirrors can be controlled to within several nm RMS. Optical polishing additionally has the potential to attain more precise surface, which means that All-CFRP mirrors were demonstrated as sufficiently accurate for use in space telescopes.

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